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**THE ETHICS OF CARE IN MAY SINCLAIR'S
PSYCHOLOGICAL NOVELS¹⁹**

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Olha Honcharova. The ethics of Care in May Sinclair's psychological novels.

*This paper examines the application of the ethics-of-care framework in May Sinclair's *The Three Sisters* (1914), *Mary Olivier: A Life* (1919), and *Life and Death of Harriett Frean* (1922). These works, often regarded as Sinclair's psychological trilogy, critique patriarchal values and explore the moral complexities of caregiving and relationality. Drawing on feminist care ethics developed by philosophers like Carol Gilligan and Nel Noddings, the analysis reveals Sinclair's portrayal of care as both an oppressive duty and a site of self-sacrificial love. Each novel presents distinct narratives reflecting these dualities, with characters grappling between personal fulfilment and societal expectations. Sinclair's incisive depictions critique possessive maternal care, oppressive societal norms, and the internalisation of moral absolutism. Her engagement with psychoanalytic thought and the cultural shifts of Edwardian society further inform the nuanced portrayal of care ethics in her narratives. Ultimately, Sinclair's exploration underscores the tension between autonomy and caregiving, challenging simplistic moral frameworks and illuminating the complexities of women's roles in familial and social contexts. Through this lens, her novels profoundly contribute to feminist literary discourse and ethical philosophy.*

Keywords: *ethics of care, May Sinclair, psychological novel, psychoanalysis, self-sacrifice, patriarchal society, values.*

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May Sinclair, a prominent modernist writer, critic, and poet, was one of the founders of the Medico-Psychological Clinic in London and a psychoanalytic thinker, who “was not only incorporating psychoanalytical ideas into her fiction” but “was writing psychoanalytic papers herself” (Bowler & Drewery, 2017, p. 7). Her psychological prose provides a rich context for examining care ethics, a feminist philosophical perspective that emphasises relationality, interdependence, and the moral significance of care (Honcharova, 2019; 2023). This paper explores the application of the ethics-of-care framework to the literary characters and interpersonal dynamics in Sinclair’s novels *The Three Sisters* (1914), *Mary Olivier: A Life* (1919), and *Life and Death of Harriett Frean* (1922), widely considered a “psychological trilogy” in her oeuvre.

The ethics of care emerged as a feminist critique of traditional moral philosophies that privilege abstract principles like justice and autonomy over relational and emotional dimensions of human life. Philosophers such as Carol Gilligan and Nel Noddings have argued that care is a fundamental aspect of human existence and a critical lens for understanding moral relationships. Noddings asserts that “caring involves stepping out of one’s own personal frame of reference into the other’s”. She continues, “When we care, we consider the other’s point of view, [their] objective needs, and what [they] expect of us. Our attention, our engrossment, is on the cared-for, not on ourselves. Our reasons for acting, then, have to do both with the other’s wants and desires and with the objective elements of [one’s] problematic situation” (Noddings, 1984, p. 24). Central to this framework are themes of vulnerability, responsibility, and the moral weight of personal and contextual relationships. Applying this lens to Sinclair’s work reveals her incisive critique of patriarchal structures, her focus on female subjectivity, and her exploration of the tension between selfhood and care for others. Sinclair’s characters are deeply embedded in familial and social networks, often navigating ethical dilemmas that challenge their autonomy and capacity for care.

Across *The Three Sisters*, *Mary Olivier*, and *Harriett Frean*, Sinclair explores the core themes from an ethics-of-care perspective, presented as a binary opposition: care as oppression and care as self-sacrifice. Sinclair’s heroines are frequently positioned as

caregivers, reflecting the historical context of women's roles in Edwardian society. Caregiving is often depicted as both a moral obligation and a source of oppression, limiting women's ability to pursue self-actualisation. The novels interrogate the balance between selfhood and care for others as Sinclair's characters grapple with moral responsibilities within familial and social contexts, highlighting the tension between individual desires and collective well-being.

While themes of caregiving and sacrifice are pervasive across Sinclair's novels, each text presents distinct perspectives within the ethics of care framework. *The Three Sisters* centres on the Cartaret sisters – Mary, Gwenda, and Alice – and their complex relationships with the charismatic Dr. Rowcliffe. The novel explores how the sisters' caregiving roles, shaped by their pursuit of personal fulfilment, reflect their distinct psychological dispositions. Having fallen in love with the same man, the sisters respond differently as rivals. Gwenda, the independent and self-reliant middle sister with the highest likelihood of marrying Rowcliffe, sacrifices her relationship with him to protect Alice, whose sexual frustration has driven her to neurosis. Alice, acutely aware of her sister's sacrifice, reciprocates by rejecting Gwenda's act of self-denial to preserve their bond. In contrast, Mary, the eldest, aligns with patriarchal societal norms, employing manipulative behaviour to secure Rowcliffe's marriage, thereby fulfilling familial and societal expectations. This intricate interplay of caregiving, rivalry, and conformity highlights the tension between individual desires and relational obligations.

In *Mary Olivier*, Sinclair offers an introspective exploration of a woman's lifelong struggle to reconcile her intellectual aspirations with her caregiving responsibilities. Mary's relationship with her domineering mother, Mrs. Olivier, epitomises the ethical tensions of care: "Ever since I began to grow up I felt there was something about Mamma that would kill me if I let it. I've had to fight for every single thing I've ever wanted. It's awful fighting her when she's so sweet and gentle" (Sinclair, 2002, p. 287). Mrs. Olivier demands unwavering devotion, stifling Mary's intellectual and emotional growth, and cares only for "a good girl" who is "submissive, domestic and religious" – essentially, a reflection of herself (Truran, 2017, p. 90). Sinclair's critique of maternal care as

possessive and manipulative aligns with care ethics' emphasis on the importance of fostering autonomy within caregiving relationships. Mary's ultimate rejection of marriage and conventional domesticity can be read as a radical assertion of her right to self-care and intellectual freedom. Yet, her decision is not without moral ambiguity. Sinclair presents Mary's solitude as both a liberation and a form of loss, illustrating the challenges of navigating a world where care and autonomy are often at odds.

In *Harriett Frean: Life and Death*, Sinclair provides a stark portrayal of care ethics through the lens of self-deception and moral failure. Harriett's life is shaped by her adherence to the Victorian ideal of "selfless" womanhood, which Sinclair critiques as a pernicious form of moral absolutism. Harriett's refusal to marry her friend's fiancé, despite their mutual love, exemplifies her internalisation of duty over personal happiness. As Harriett ages, her adherence to these ideals isolates her, leaving her life devoid of meaningful relationships. Sinclair's portrayal of Harriett's "care" exposes its hollowness, as it is rooted not in genuine concern for others but in adherence to socially constructed norms. The novel's bleak conclusion underscores the ethical dangers of subordinating relational care to abstract moral principles.

Sinclair's exploration of care ethics must be understood within the broader cultural and historical context of her time. Writing in the early 20th century, she was deeply influenced by the rise of psychoanalysis, the suffrage movement, and the shifting roles of women in Edwardian society. Her novels reflect the tensions between traditional gender roles and the emerging feminist consciousness. For instance, the suffrage movement's emphasis on women's rights and autonomy resonates with Sinclair's critique of self-sacrificial care. At the same time, her psychoanalytic interests inform her nuanced portrayal of caregiving as a site of both emotional connection and psychic conflict. The characters in Sinclair's "psychological trilogy" embody these tensions, navigating the complexities of care in ways that resist easy moral categorisation.

Sinclair's novels thus offer a profound exploration of the ethics of care, illuminating the moral complexities of caregiving and relationality. Through her depictions of female

subjectivity and interdependence, she critiques the patriarchal values that devalue care while exposing the challenges inherent in balancing care and autonomy.

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